

THE ROLES OF *CAPSICUM* IN DIABETES MELLITUS

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes is a major degenerative disease affecting at least 15 million people and having complications which include hypertension, atherosclerosis and microcirculatory disorders. At least 80% of Africans rely on plant medicine for their healthcare in the management of diabetes and other diseases. The present review paper unveils the roles of *Capsicum* in diabetes mellitus. The review reported *Capsicum* to possess hypoglycemic, insulinomimetic or secretagogues properties, weight reducing effect and hypolipidemic properties in diabetes. The roles played by *Capsicum* in diabetes could be traced to its antioxidant properties embedded in its phytoconstituents. We recommend further research on this plant.

KEYWORDS: *Capsicum*, Diabetes mellitus, Hypoglycemia, Phytochemicals, *Capsiacin*, *Capsicum annuum* and Blood glucose.

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a multifactorial disease which is characterized by hyperglycemia (Scoppola, *et al.*, 2001), lipoprotein abnormalities (Scoppola, *et al.*, 2001), raised basal metabolic rate (Avesani, *et al.*, 2001), defect in reactive oxygen species scavenging enzymes and altered intermediary metabolism of major food substances (Avesani, *et al.*, 2001). Commonly referred to as a syndrome, diabetes is classified into three types, namely, type 1 diabetes, type 2 diabetes and gestational diabetes. The classical symptoms of diabetes are polyuria (frequent urination), polydipsia (increased thirst) and polyphagia (increased hunger), (Cooke and Plotnick, 2008). Hyperglycemia plays a critical role in the development and progression of Diabetic complications, through a number of mechanisms including increased oxidative stress, metabolic problems and infection, (Sailaja, *et al.*, 2003).

Diabetes is a major degenerative disease in the world today, affecting at least 15 million people and having complications which include hypertension, atherosclerosis, Neuropathy, Nephropathy, Retinopathy, Gastropathy microcirculatory disorders, and sexual dysfunction (Aragno, *et al.*, 1999). Liver disease among others is associated with diabetes (Elizabeth and Harris, 2005, Chatila and West, 1996).

The number of diabetic patient is expected to increase from 171 million in year 2000 to 366 million or more by year 2030 (Wild, *et al.*, 2004) which had already been declared epidemic by WHO.

Irrespective of the great strides that have been made in the understanding and management of diabetes, the disease and its complication are increasingly persisting. Insulin and various oral antidiabetic agents such as insulin, sulfonylureas, biguanides and glinides are the currently available therapies for diabetes. However, many of them have a number of serious adverse effects ranging from lipodystrophy, weight gain, allergic reactions and hypoglycemia among others (Richard and Pamella, 2009), therefore, the search for more effective and safer hypoglycemic agents is one of the important areas of investigation, (Saxena and Vikram, 2004).

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Several medicinal plants which have been experimentally explored to be useful in diabetes having hypoglycemic activity worldwide are available in literatures. However, searching for new antidiabetic drugs from natural plants is still very useful because they contain substances which demonstrate alternative and safe effects on diabetes mellitus. Most of plants containing glycosides, alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids, carotenoids, etc., are frequently implicated as having antidiabetic effect (Malviya, *et al.*, 2010).

Fruits and vegetables have been recognized as natural sources of various bioactive compounds (Pennington and Fisher, 2010 ; Dembitsky, *et al.*, 2011). The main phytochemical compounds present in fruits and vegetables are flavonoids, anthocyanins, vitamins C and E, phenolic compounds, dietary fiber, and carotenoids (Ayala-Zavala, *et al.*, 2011). A lower risk of developing various chronic diseases has been attributed to these phytochemicals, in particular to their antioxidant and radical-scavenging activities (González-Aguilar, *et al.*, 2008). The hypoglycemic effect of several fruits and vegetables used as antidiabetic remedies has been confirmed, and the mechanisms of hypoglycemic activity of such are being studied (ALHowiriny, *et al.*, 2005).

Several studies showed that there is a relationship between consumption of fruits and vegetables and the development of these disorders (Yahia, 2011). Epidemiological studies showed that antioxidant compounds in the fruits and vegetables can terminate a free radical chain reaction (Basma, 2011) which is capable of preventing diseases such as cardiovascular disease, cancer and diabetes (Basma, 2011).

This review focuses majorly on the role of *Capsicum* in diabetes. Natural products including fruits and vegetables spices have been shown to possess antidiabetic potential which acts through either insulinomimetic or secretagogues properties, (Jung, *et al.*, 2006). One such vegetable spice crops is the pepper. Pepper belongs to the genus *Capsicum*, a Solanaceae family, which comprised of more than 200 varieties, with *Capsicum annum*, *Capsicum baccatum*, *Capsicum chinense*, *Capsicum frutescens*, and *Capsicum pubescens* being the main five species (Zimmer, *et al.*, 2012, Menichini, *et al.*, 2009). *Capsicum* can be annual or short-lived perennial plant. The flowers are white with greenish white or greenish yellow corolla and are either insect or self- fertilized the plant berries typically grow erect; ellipsoid-conical to lanceoloid shaped. They are usually very small and pungent, growing to 10-20mm long and 3-7mm in diameter. The fruits of most varieties are red; some are yellow, purple or black. The fruits are somewhat dry and contain few to many (depending on fruit size) cream to yellow lenticular seeds about 3 mm in diameter. The fruits, especially the seeds and placenta, have biting, pungent taste, (Bailey 1941, Bentley and Trimer, 1880).

Common names of *Capsicum* include; Cayenne Pepper, Red Pepper, African Bird Pepper, Bird Pepper, Spanish Pepper, American Red Pepper. Peppers are consumed worldwide and their importance has increased gradually to place them among the most consumed spice crops in the world (Bown, 2001).

Historically, *Capsicum* was first described in the mid-1400s by a physician who accompanied Columbus to the West Indies. The plants derive their names from the Latin *capsa* (box), which refers to the partially hollow, box-like fruit. *Capsicum* has been highly desired as a spice and has been cultivated in some form in almost every society. Peppers are among the most widely consumed spices in the world, with an average daily per capita consumption in some Southeast Asian countries approaching 5 g of red pepper, corresponding to approximately 50 mg of capsaicin (Leung, 1980).

PHYTOCHEMISTRY

The major active ingredient present in *Capsicum* include homocapsaicin, norhydrocapsaicin, dihydrocapsaicin, and homodihydrocapsaicin. Flavonoids, fatty acids, carotene, vitamins A and C, citric, tartaric, malic and tannic acids, magnesium, phosphorus, sulphur, B-complex vitamins, sodium, selenium and thiamine have also been identified in the fruits. The red color present in *Capsicum* is due to its very high content of vitamin A, which is vital for normal vision, cellular activity, growth and strong immune defenses, (Howard, 2000).

MEDICINAL VALUES

Pepper are usually consumed as food and used as additives in the food industry. They also have a significant role in traditional medicine. It is used traditionally as analgesic, antibacterial, antioxidant, antipyretic,

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antiseptic,, antispasmodic, aromatic, astringent, blood thinner, cardiovascular tonic, carminative, circulatory stimulant, diaphoretic, hemostatic,, herbal accentuator, nerve stimulant, stomachic and tonic (general), (Buck and Buck, 1983).

The active substance found in pepper (capsicum) that gives hot and spicy flavor is capsaicin, and it seems to have many pharmacological effects. The structure of capsaicin (8-methyl-N-vanillyl-6-nonenamide) is similar to that of eugenol, the active principle in oil of cloves, which can also induce long-lasting local analgesia (Gonzalez, 1983). Capsaicin triggers the release of the neuropeptide P from the sensory nerve fibers of the C type. In mammals, capsaicin binds to the TRPV1 vanilloid receptor. The TRPV1 receptor then releases sensory neuropeptides that trigger a neurogenic inflammatory response, (Pall, *et al.*, 2004).

CAPSICUM AND DIABETES

In diabetes various species of Capsicum had been reported to show several benefits. *Capsicum frutescens* has been used to treat diabetes mellitus by traditional healers in Jamaica, (Block and Langseth, 1994). Purification experiments employing thin layer chromatography (TLC) and high performance liquid chromatography which led to the extraction of the active principle, capsaicin is now known to reduce the blood sugar level. Traditionally the people from Jamaica have been using this vegetable to treat Type 2 Diabetes. In a research, Capsaicin was given to six experimental rats with diabetes. Before the experiment, the blood sugar level in the rats was around 6.40mmol/dL. After the experiment, the blood sugar was found to be around 4.91mmol/dL and a drop of 23% in the blood sugar level was noted.

In a research carried out to clarify whether a low or a high, but tolerable, dietary dose of red chilli (RC) can ameliorate the diabetes related complications in a high-fat (HF) diet-fed streptozotocin (STZ)-induced type 2 diabetes model of rats, five-week-old male Sprague Dawley rats were fed a HF diet for 2 weeks then randomly divided into four groups namely: normal control (NC), diabetic control (DBC), red chilli low (RCL, 0.5%) and red chilli high (RCH, 2.0%) groups. Diabetes was induced by an intraperitoneal (i.p.) injection of STZ (40 mg/kg BW) in all groups except the NC group. After 4 weeks feeding of experimental diets, the fasting blood glucose concentrations in both RC fed groups were not significantly different. The serum insulin concentration was significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased in the RCH group compared with the DBC and RCL groups. Blood HbA1c, liver weight, liver glycogen and serum lipids were not influenced by the feeding of RC-containing diets. The data of this study suggest that 2% dietary RC is insulinotropic rather than hypoglycemic (Yazar, *et al.*, 2008).

In another research, a crossover study was performed in 12 healthy volunteers by performing the oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) while receiving placebo or 5 grams of capsicum. The insulin secretion and capsaicin level in plasma were measured using the HPLC method. The results of the OGTT showed that plasma glucose levels in volunteers who received capsicum were significantly lower than those in the placebo group at 30 and 45 minutes ($P < 0.05$). Furthermore, plasma insulin levels were significantly higher at 60, 75, 105, and 120 minutes ($P < 0.05$). When comparing before and after capsicum intake, the results showed the insulin levels were maintained. The study found that 5 grams of capsicum presented capsaicin levels that were associated with a decrease in plasma glucose levels and the maintenance of insulin levels. (Kamon, *et al.*, 2009).

In another study, a reduction in postprandial hyperinsulinemia was achieved with 30 g of freshly chopped chili daily over 4 weeks, but no reduction in the glucose area under the curve (AUC) or peak glucose levels were shown (Ahuja, *et al.*, 2006). The cholesterol lowering effect of cayenne is also reported in medically.

Antioxidant activity has been demonstrated in vitro and in the clinical setting (Sun, *et al.*, 2007) but with no significant difference in serum lipids, lipoproteins, or total antioxidant status (Ahuja and Ball, 2006).

Capsicum has been used for weight reduction, although clinical evidence is insufficient to support this use (Kang, *et al.*, 2007). A clinical trial evaluated the safety of 6 mg/day of capsaicinoids over 12 weeks for weight loss, while another study used 30 g/day of fresh chili containing approximately 55% cayenne chili for 4 weeks

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(Ahuja and Ball, 2006). Weight loss was not achieved in either trial. Loss of abdominal fat was achieved in the 12-week trial (Snitker, *et al.*, 2009).

Anti-diabetic and anti-hypertension-relevant potential of phenolic phytochemicals had also been confirmed in selected nine types of commonly available pepper varieties using *in vitro* enzyme assays for alpha-glucosidase, alpha-amylase and angiotensin I-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitory activities. The *in vitro* inhibitory activities of these enzymes provide a strong biochemical rationale for further *in vivo* studies and dietary management strategy for type 2 diabetes through the control of glucose absorption and reduction of associated hypertension. In the study, Pepper (*Capsicum annuum*) – Green, Red, Orange, Yellow, Cubanelle, Red sweet, Yellow sweet, Long hot and Jalapenonine types of pepper were investigated for inhibitory activity against said enzymes. From the result, several pepper extracts had high a-glucosidase inhibitory activity, which was not correlated to total phenolic content and free radical scavenging-linked antioxidant activity. Select extracts such as Green pepper and Long hot pepper had less or no inhibitory effect on the a-amylase activity, which indicates the potential for reduced side effects. Among various water extracts, Yellow, Cubanelle and Red pepper had the highest ACE inhibitory activity. Therefore, combinations of pepper could be screened for dietary management of type 2 diabetes, associated hypertension and microvascular complications linked to oxidative dysfunction, and provide the basis for clinical studies (Young-In, *et al.*, 2007).

CONCLUSION

Plants have been a good source of medicine for the treatment of various type of disease, still many plants and active compounds obtained from plants have not been well. Natural products classified into terpenoids, alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, and some other categories have shown antidiabetic potential. In this review, Capsicum has been characterized to have active phytoconstituents with blood glucose lowering effect as well as having insulin mimetics or insulin secretagogues potential and can be used to treat various types of secondary complications of diabetes mellitus.

RECOMMENDATIONS

More investigations should be carried out to evaluate the exact mechanism of action behind the antidiabetic and insulinomimetic activity in Capsicum. Sub-acute and chronic toxicity studies should also be carried out in animal models.

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